

A STUDY ON WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY AND EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

AYESHA PARVEEN.S

MBA Student, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai.

Dr. BENITA S. MONICA, B.E., MBA., Ph.D.

Assistant Professor, Saveetha School of Management, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai. Email: benitasmonica.ssm@saveetha.com

ABSTRACT:

This article concentrates on the workplace spirituality and employee engagement of employees in the IT Industry. The paramount objective of this study is to know about the importance and benefits of employee engagement and workplace spirituality in the organizations. There were many hindrances and problems which arise in the organization because of lack of maintenance of human resource personnel. In this article descriptive methodology has been adopted to extract the appropriate results. The response was collected by circulating a questionnaire. The questionnaire got 50 respondents. The main focus was to understand about the power of engaged and spiritual employees. The results of the study interpret that employee engagement and workplace spirituality increases the productivity, and reduces absenteeism and also increases job satisfaction and motivation of the employees.

KEYWORDS: Workplace spirituality, Employee engagement, organizational commitment, productivity, sustainable development, turnover, IT employees.

INTRODUCTION:

In this competitive edge, workplace spirituality and employee engagement are some of the major factors which drives the organization to success. These elements not only help to reach higher productivity, employee retention and job satisfaction but also to bring customer satisfaction and company reputation. High level of employee engagement occurs when employees are spiritually connected, committed, enthusiastic and passionate to work. There are many researches focused on employee engagement and spirituality aspects which reap both financial and non-financial benefit. Several studies shows that human resources are the most significant factors for organizations to survive and prosper. Successful organization mostly pay attention to employee engagement, workplace spirituality and brand loyalty. Engaged and spiritual employees work with passion towards the organizational goals. Employers need to find alternative ways of recognition and respect upon employees to do their part in meeting the spiritual needs of the employees. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; David, Ahmed, Ganeshkumar & Sankar, 2020; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Sankar and Suresh (2018) have discussed about the modelling factors of workplace spirituality in healthcare organization. The main purpose of this study is to prove that spirituality is very important entity in every organization. This paper critically studies about the influential factors of workplace spirituality. Healthcare sector employees are taken as sample for this study. The model of Interpretive structural modelling (ISM) which analyses the modelling factors such as organizational commitment, job overload, learning culture, work satisfaction, intention to leave, sense of responsibility, employee commitment, employee engagement, environmental passion and pro environmental behavior. The findings of this study proves that spirituality increases productivity in the organization.

Mehta and Mehta (2013) have studied about the importance of employee engagement in organization. This paper concentrates to study about the dimensions of employee engagement. Employees working in an organization are taken as samples for the study. Robinson's (2004) model and Penna's (2007) Hierarchical model was used to arrive at the conclusion. These models concentrate on the fulfillment of employees at workplace and found that dynamic psychological process determines the employee engagement and productivity in the organization.

Lee, Shin, Park, Kim and Cho (2017) have discussed about the employee engagement in the field of Human Resource Development. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the discussion of Employee engagement in the four representative journals that is (HRDI), (HRDR), (HRDQ), (ADHR). The study selected 10 empirical articles and 14 conceptual articles for review and analyzed the current state of employee engagement in Human Resource Development. The results conclude that employee engagement increases the employee's skills and talents for future development.

Chandani, Mehta, Mall and Khokhar (2016) have studied about the importance of employee engagement and its influence on employee retention and performance in organizations. The samples are 30 academic and popular research papers pertaining to employee engagement. In this paper there is no one fixed model that shows relevance. The findings of this study shows that employee engagement results in decline in employee turnover intention and increases employee's innovative work-related behavior.

Daniel (2015) has discussed on the three dimensions of workplace spirituality and stress. The study was conducted in Mexico and USA with a sample of 304 individuals from both countries. Structural equation modelling is used as a tool for deriving the results. The findings of this study is conducting meaningful activities in the workplaces reduces stress of the employees. These results can give guidance to human resource managers and business specialist to understand about the workplace spirituality and work stress.

Kumar and Kumar (2014) have studied about the role of workplace spirituality in relation with stress. This paper critically investigates the relationship between occupational stress and health of the personnel. The study used managers as sample. A sample of 150 managers were given a 28-item questionnaire to derive the results. This paper analyzed the results with

Cronbach's alpha scale and shows results as workplace spirituality helps to cope up with stress within an organization.

Pradhan, Pradhan and Jens (2016) have discussed on the workplace spirituality and job outcomes in Indian information technology industry. The main purpose of this study is to examine the effect of workplace spirituality on two components, i.e., affective organizational commitment and job satisfaction. The responses are taken from 480 IT professionals from various organizations in India. The study used conceptual model which connects the workplace spirituality with affective organizational commitment and job satisfaction and analysed the results with model fit analysis. The study concludes that workplace spirituality has positive influence on employee's job outcomes.

Ram and Prabhakar (2011) have studied about the employee engagement in work related outcomes. The study shows that employee engagement is one of the top five most important aspect in every organization. The respondents of the study are 656 CEOs from different countries. The research model used in this study comprises of the major aspects in employee engagement i.e., job satisfaction, job involvement, OCB and other perceived support. The results of the study prove that employee engagement increases employee motivation, attendance, retention and productivity in the organization.

Utami, Sapta, Verawati, Astakoni (2021) has discussed about the relationship between workplace spirituality, organizational citizenship behavior and organizational commitment. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of work behavior of employees in the organization. The sample of the study are 80 employees of 12 village credit institutions. The data was collected through interviews and questionnaires. The study used structural model and measurement model to predict the results. The findings suggested that workplace spirituality does not affects organizational citizenship behavior but positively affects organizational commitment.

Barik and Kochar (2017) has discussed about the antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. The study focuses on different aspects of employee engagement. The author proposed his own model with the key driving aspects of employee engagement. The model comprises of reward system, job enrichment, effective leadership, employment security as drivers and the results were employee satisfaction, improved productivity and improved employee turnover. Thus, employee engagement results in gaining high satisfaction, high productivity and absenteeism in the organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In this article, descriptive research methodology is used to find the results. The employees of IT Industry were taken as sample respondents for the study. Questionnaire are used to collect data from 50 respondents using Google form. The questionnaire includes questions regarding Demographics, workplace spirituality and employee engagement. The items depicting workplace spirituality and employee engagement are measured using 5-point Likert scale. The sample profile is depicted in the table 1 below.

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents.

S.NO	DEMOGRAPHICS	PERCENTAGE
1.	GENDER Male Female	28% 72%
2.	AGE Below 20 years 21-30 years 31-40 years Above 40 years	30% 70% 0% 0%
3.	MARITAL STATUS Single Married	92% 8%
4.	EXPERIENCE 0-1 years 1-3 years More than 3 years	76% 14% 8%

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

The data collected is analyzed using IBM SPSS 26. The statistical tools used are Percentage analysis, Mean Analysis and Linear regression. The results obtained are tabulated and explained below.

MEAN ANALYSIS:

Table No. 2: Mean Analysis of Employee Engagement

S.NO	PARTICULARS	MEAN	RANK
1.	Participation in meetings	2.4000	3
2.	Risk or initiative	2.4800	1
3.	Chance to express opinion	2.3400	4
4.	Coordination with boss	2.4400	2
5.	Learning experience	1.8200	5

The table reports the mean values and the respective ranking of factors in employee engagement. The results suggests that the initiative and risk taken by the employees and coordination with supervisor contributes majorly to employee engagement in organizations. The employees should concentrate more on expressing their opinion to gain experience and to learn new skills. Overall employee engagement plays a vital role in increasing coordination and participation of employees.

Table No. 3: Mean Analysis of Workplace Spirituality

S. No	PARTICULARS	MEAN	RANK
1.	Sense of enlightenment	2.5400	2
2.	Blissful moments at work	2.5600	1
3.	Spiritual value guides my decision	2.3200	4
4.	Joy and happiness at work	2.2200	5
5.	Feel elevated at work	2.3600	3

The table reports the mean values and the respective ranking of factors in workplace spirituality. The results suggests that the intensity with the employees spiritual sense makes the employees feel blissful at work and also creates a sense of enlightenment at work. Though the efforts of the employees are important for the work to be done, at the same lane the employees spiritual values have an extra measure to perform their best at work. The result suggests that if the employees feel more blissful and enlightened there will be better coordination in the organization and it instills that decision making is not guided by workplace spirituality.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table No. 4: Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	Std error of the estimate
.562	.316	.301	.73398

Table No. 5: ANOVA

Model	Sum Of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11.920	1	11.920	22.126	.000
Residual	25.859	48	.539		
Total	37.779	49			

Table No. 6: COEFFICIENTS

Model B	Std Error	Beta	T	Sig.
Constant	-.104	.521	-.200	.843
Workplace spirituality	.213	.562	4.704	.000

R, the multiple correlation coefficient, specifies the significance of prediction of the predicted variable. In model, R value of 0.562 indicates that workplace spirituality aspects are good predictors of employee engagement. R², coefficient of determination, represents the level of variation in predicted variable explained by the predictor variable. In this model, 31.6% of variance in employee engagement is positively influenced by some aspects of workplace

spirituality. Productivity, reduction in turnover of employees, increased motivation are the significant ($p < 0.000$) predictors of workplace spirituality and all are positive predictors. When the employees are engaged and have mutual coordination between them and maintain spirituality in the workplace, there will be positive environment in the organization.

DISCUSSION:

In recent years, there were many articles which contribute which pay attention to employee engagement and workplace spirituality. There were not only concepts and dimensions but also antecedents and outcomes. The results of the study show that employee engagement has positive influence on workplace spirituality. Similar findings were reported by other researchers. In a study by Walt and Herman reported that workplace spirituality is one of the important factors for job involvement and investigated that workplace spirituality can be a predictor of positive work-related attitudes. And another study by Thomas Reio reported that their research has limitations and there is need for additional research. Some studies show contradictory results for the same. A study by Qandeel malik shows that employee engagement creates salary hike, opportunity training which is an expense to the organization. As there were many studies which support and as well which contradict the results derived from this study. There were many articles which have a same conclusion like this study and portray the same level of significance the findings of this study show the challenging factors to be controlled by every organization. The spirituality aspects of the study are the main independent variables which show positive influence when compared with employee engagement. Thus it indicates that if the employees are engaged, predominantly there will be highest chance for spirituality. The main purpose of this study is to give a descriptive explanation about employee engagement and workplace spirituality and to sort out the confusions regarding the same.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the study show that employee engagement has positive influence on workplace spirituality. Workplace spirituality is very important to interconnect between the past experiences and to develop mutual trust among the employees. The present study attempted to provide comprehensive understanding of the importance of workplace spirituality and employee engagement. To maintain an engaged workforce and workplace spirituality, organizations need to implement strategies such as continuous monitoring to reduce malpractice, facilitating employees with the required and adequate resources as and when needed which may increase the productivity and enlighten the joy and happiness at the workplace. Workplace spirituality enhances the performance of the employees and enlighten the day to day activities of the employees. The main factor which positively influences workplace spirituality are productivity which is because of the properly engaged employees. The study focus on the inference where workplace spirituality and employee engagement coincides and creates a better environment in the organization. The era of organizational citizenship behaviour has been increasing in the last decades, thus prevailing way for better coordination and understanding in the workplace. Every employee should adapt to the norms and requirements of the organization to have a better workplace. If the strategies of the

organization as well as the mutual cooperation of the employees prevails, then there will be a perfect balance between the employee engagement and workplace spirituality. The results shows that productivity, turnover, satisfaction, motivation are the factors of employee engagement which positively influences workplace spirituality. There were many unanswered queries regarding employee engagement and workplace spirituality and there were many conceptual and empirical researches preaching the results. Though, this study inculcates in a manner where the results are positive and coincides with each other. In this study, descriptive method of research methodology is used to derive the results. And as per the information mentioned above workplace spirituality and employee engagement are some of the critical aspect to which every organization should give utmost importance for a better organizational climate and organizational commitment.

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